

Table S1. Functional enrichment of EZH2 co-expressed genes

Term	Count	P-Value	Fold	FDR
Cluster 1, Score: 86.8				
GO:0022403~cell cycle phase	89	4.47E-90	17.3	6.86E-87
GO:0000279~M phase	82	1.06E-87	20.1	1.62E-84
GO:0022402~cell cycle process	94	6.78E-85	13.4	1.04E-81
Cluster 2, Score: 72.7				
GO:0000278~mitotic cell cycle	78	1.05E-76	17.0	1.61E-73
GO:0007067~mitosis	65	5.08E-73	23.8	7.80E-70
GO:0000280~nuclear division	65	5.08E-73	23.8	7.80E-70
GO:0000087~M phase of mitotic cell cycle	65	1.91E-72	23.4	2.94E-69
GO:0048285~organelle fission	65	9.64E-72	22.9	1.48E-68
Cluster 3, Score: 16.0				
GO:0006974~response to DNA damage stimulus	34	2.32E-19	7.4	3.57E-16
GO:0006281~DNA repair	28	9.77E-17	7.9	1.67E-13
GO:0033554~cellular response to stress	34	5.96E-14	4.8	9.14E-11
Cluster 4, Score: 12.0				
GO:0051327~M phase of meiotic cell cycle	16	9.41E-13	13.1	1.45E-09
GO:0007126~meiosis	16	9.41E-13	13.1	1.45E-09
GO:0051321~meiotic cell cycle	16	1.28E-12	12.9	1.96E-09
Cluster, Annotation Cluster; Score, Enrichment Score; Fold, Fold Enhancement; FDR, False Discovery Rate				